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Linus Pauling on Vitamin C

To the Editor:

In your March 16 Week in Review article¹ “A No Vote on Vitamin C” reference is made to two papers in the Journal of the American Medical Society, one a study of vitamin C in relation to the common cold conducted at the National Institutes of Health,² and the other a survey of previous studies.³ The authors concluded that vitamin C had “at best only a minor influence on the duration and severity of colds.”

Three important studies were ignored in the survey. Twelve controlled studies have been carried out in which subjects exposed to cold viruses in the ordinary way, by contact with other people, regularly received vitamin C, an average of 1,000 milligrams per day, and other subjects received an inactive tablet. Every one of these twelve studies gave the result that the vitamin C subjects had less illness than the control subjects. The average amount of decreased illness for the vitamin C subjects was 37 per cent.

There is no doubt that vitamin C, taken regularly, leads to a significant protection against colds for most people. In addition, extra vitamin C taken at the first sign of a cold in amounts of about one gram per hour may stop a cold. The authors of the report in the Journal of the American Medical Association may consider this effect to be “a minor influence”; I consider it to be important.

LINUS PAULING

President, Linus Pauling Institute of Science and Medicine

Menlo Park, Calif., March 20, 1975

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- 1 Schmeck HM (1975 Mar. 11) 2 Reports Find Little Merit in Using Vitamin C to Treat Colds.
<https://www.nytimes.com/1975/03/11/archives/2-reports-find-little-merit-in-using-vitamin-c-to-treat-colds.html>
<https://timesmachine.nytimes.com/timesmachine/1975/03/11/78827425.html?pageNumber=14>
 - 2 Karlowski TR, Chalmers TC, Frenkel LD, Kapikian AZ, Lewis TL, Lynch JM (1975) Ascorbic acid for the common cold: a prophylactic and therapeutic trial. JAMA 231:1038-42.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/163386>
 - 3 Dykes MHM, Meier P (1975) Ascorbic acid and the common cold: evaluation of its efficacy and toxicity. JAMA 231:1073-9.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1089817>
See Pauling’s comments on the 1975 review in JAMA:
(1976a) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11546757>
(1976b) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11547088>